

CREATION AND IMPROVEMENT OF BRANDING ACTIVITY OF JV LLC "SIYOB SAKHOVATI"

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7063974>

Abstract. This article discusses the properties, benefits, value, individuality of the product and the company needs to form a brand strategy that would increase the effectiveness of marketing activities in general.

Keywords: assortment, brand of goods, enterprise, characteristic, potential, activity, recommendation.

СОЗДАНИЕ И СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ БРЕНДИНГОВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СП ООО «СИЁБ САХОВАТИ»

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются свойства, преимущества, ценность, индивидуальность продукта и потребности компании в формировании стратегии бренда, которая повысила бы эффективность маркетинговой деятельности в целом.

Ключевые слова: ассортимент, марка товара, предприятие, характеристика, потенциал, деятельность, рекомендация.

INTRODUCTION

In the assortment policy, it is developed and actively used by all leading firms - this is branding activity. EnterpriseJV ООО "Siyob sahovati" among other recommendations, we consider it necessary to form a program of activities for the development of the brand. This activity is already used in the Siyob group of companies under the Pure Milk brand. In addition, the modern literature describes the main materials on the creation and expansion of branding activities, in this section we present materials from foreign companies that successfully work with the brand.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A trademark carries a certain set of properties, benefits and services to the buyer; it serves as an emblem that informs consumers of some information about the product. A trademark can carry up to four different meanings:

1. Properties. A brand is associated with certain properties of a product. In advertising, a company can use several properties of its product at once.
2. Benefits. Customers buy benefits, not features, for example, the "reliable" feature can be thought of as a functional benefit like "I won't need to be replaced..."
3. Value. A trademark carries information about the value system of the buyer.
4. Individuality. A trademark is a reflection of individuality. The brand will attract those buyers whose actual or desired self-perception matches the image created by the brand.

So, we can conclude that a trademark is a complex symbol, and that companies should not treat it as an ordinary product name, thereby ignoring the purpose of the brand as such. The marketer must decide at what level of brand value the image will be built. "The most enduring and enduring qualities of a brand are its core value and identity. It is these qualities that define the essence of each brand.

When creating a trademark, companies can choose one of the levels and direct their efforts to it:

1. A single brand of the company. For example, "Philips", "Heinz", "Mercedes Benz" have the same trademark as the names of the respective companies and are assigned to most of the goods they produce. Turning to this strategy allows you to achieve cost reduction, as it eliminates the need for research on the patent purity of new names and advertising aimed at increasing brand awareness.

2. Individual brand names. For example, companies such as Procter & Gamble, Unilever have developed trademarks for each of their products ("Persil", "Fairy", "Domestos", etc.). The main advantage of this strategy is that the company does not associate its own reputation with the attitude of consumers towards a particular product.

3. A combination of branded and individual names. For example, Kellogg's uses dual personal-brand names, thereby adhering to the "golden mean". The name of the company gives the new product fame, and the individual brand name - originality.

4. Groups of brands. Some companies group product groups under one (generic) brand name, for example, Matsushita Corporation supplies electronic products under the four generic names "National", "Quasar", "Technics" and "Panasonic".

Each of the levels has its own advantages. Brand names are more recognizable, economical, while individual names make it possible to segment the market, reduce the possible losses of the supplier in case of failure of one of his brands. The mixed approach is the desire to balance these two poles.

Major brands make attractive offers to buyers. Successful companies achieve competitive advantage by complementing the core product with other products and services, they seek not only to meet but also to exceed consumer expectations. For example, when buying a product, the consumer gets the opportunity to contact the company's specialists by phone for free. In this way, not only a quality product is offered, but the possibilities of "direct partnership marketing" are used to establish personal contact with customers.

The potential of brands is spoken about when its added value is so great that customers are reluctant to accept a substitute for this product, even if there are cheaper or more readily available analogues. Trust, respect, satisfaction, i.e. psychological benefits ensure the superiority of the brand and allow brands such as Coca-Cola, Gillette, Kodak to maintain leading positions in their industries for more than half a century.

Now let's turn to the description of the main characteristics of brands with high potential:

1. Product quality. Quality is the main determinant of brand value. If the quality of the product is reduced, then the position of the brand is deteriorating.

2. Be the first. Naturally, it is easier to win the favor of the consumer if the brand has no rivals. "Being first" means being the leader in a key market, not in technology. For example, digital watches were first developed by Texas Instruments but were first introduced to the mass market by Casio and Seiko.

3. Unique positioning strategy. If a company does not have the advantage of product novelty, success can be achieved with an original positioning concept that will ensure that the brand is different from its peers. For example, the Body Shop offered an ecological line of cosmetic products.

4. Specific communication program. In order to be successful, a firm needs an effective advertising campaign and promotion program. They must convey to the consumer information about the qualities of the brand and initiate trial purchases.

5. Timing and consistency. Building a successful brand takes time and long-term investment. First of all, it is necessary to direct funds to activities that promote brand acceptance by the consumer. Then you should maintain its advantages and take care that it remains "forever young." There are no short cuts to building brand equity, but the rewards for patience and perseverance are great.

RESULTS

So, first of all, it is important to have a quality product that meets the needs of customers. Then a presentation of the product is needed, which increases its attractiveness. Then it is necessary to expand the base of the brand, supplementing it with other products and services. If the brand concept is developed properly, its use generates satisfaction and the intention to repeat the purchase. But the desire to try and buy the product again is not automatic, but requires the invested efforts of the supplier. By stimulating demand, the company invests in advertising, sales, product promotion, public relations, and so on.

Building a strong brand requires careful planning and large long-term investments. The essence of a successful brand is an extraordinary product or service backed up by creatively designed and well-executed marketing.

First of all, marketing activities associated with the creation of a brand should be aimed at analyzing the market situation. To do this, it is necessary to identify the positions of competing companies, determine the desired position of the brand and its perception by consumers, take into account the current situation, production capacity, financial capabilities, experience and qualifications of personnel, market dynamics, and government regulation.

After that, you can imagine the place where the brand of the company is located, what prospects it has and in what direction it should develop.

The central step in the practice of branding is the development of a brand identity, that is, a set of unique features by which customers recognize a given brand. These signs can be not only material, but also meaningful. Brand development activity can be divided into 2 main stages:

- detection of significant differences from competitive brands, brand positioning and the formation of its concept;
- developing a brand identity - how consumers should perceive it.

DISCUSSION

So, in order for the buyer to be able to distinguish a brand among analogues, he must have an idea of how this brand differs from others. There are so-called perceptible features - size, weight, taste, smell, design, shape, and so on. These differences are most easily addressed in communications, as such differences cannot be denied. For example, the fact that there is more shampoo in a shampoo package than in a standard package.

Insensible differences exist, but they are either difficult to distinguish or not directly perceptible. In order to translate imperceptible differences into perceptible, special techniques are often used in advertising. For example, advertisements for Fairy dishwashing products show the number of clean dishes.

But if the brand does not have any significant differences, then there are imaginary differences that are "born" in marketing departments or advertising agencies and exist only in

marketing communications. It is often difficult to draw the line between imagined and imperceptible differences, for example, we do not know if bifidobacteria are actually in yogurt, ceramides are in shampoo, and xylitol is in chewing gum.

It is important to compare this brand with others. It is necessary to compare the product in such a way as to show stronger and more convincingly those obvious differences and advantages that distinguish the brand from the general range:

1. Direct comparison. Competitive brands are often compared, the advantages of one over the other are shown.

2. Average product. Direct comparisons of existing trademarks are prohibited in some countries and therefore other forms of comparison are used. One of them is a comparison with a generalized product, for example, with “ordinary toothpaste”, “ordinary washing powder”.

3. Comparison with the outdated model. A fairly common method involves comparing a given brand with a product of the previous generation. This method is used when a new revolutionary product enters the market and when the comparison is due to the fact that the new brand does not differ in any significant way from its counterparts, but looks unique and modern against the background of its predecessor.

4. Product category. This comparison is not with any product, but with a whole product category that is close in purpose, but offers a different benefit.

5. Artificial comparison. This is a comparison of a brand with a group of products with which it is actually not quite correct to compare, for example, milk soufflé with milk.

6. Comparison with what they are silent about. This is a method in which words such as “better”, “faster”, “better”, “more efficient” are used, comparing with a similar, although not named, product.

7. Comparison with yourself. It aims to give customers the impression that only this brand is real, unique and unrepeatable.

CONCLUSIONS

Comparative context is needed to state that a particular brand of product is better than others. Thus, the attention of buyers is concentrated on those advantages that are important and relevant when using this particular brand. The technique of focusing on the benefits of a product is very common in advertising: “Gillette is better for a man!”, “We try harder than others” (“Avis”), and so on.

Next, it is worth mentioning the positioning of the brand. Positioning is a marketing strategy for developing a company's offerings in order to occupy an advantageous position in the mind and psychology of the target consumer group. That is, it represents the management of the consumer's opinion regarding the place (position) of the brand among many different brands of a given or related group. The purpose of positioning is to create the impression for the consumer that he has a unique, one-of-a-kind product in front of him, that there is no equivalent replacement for this brand.

Positioning is an integral part of the image that is formed in the consumer mind and is called a brand. It is based on how consumers perceive and evaluate the purpose, benefit, quality and reliability, benefits and other characteristics of the product. It is especially important in the following cases. Firstly, when there are many goods in the product group that are close in price, quality and purpose of use. Secondly, when a manufacturing company launches several brands on the market that are in the same product category.

REFERENCES

1. Message from the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. January 24, 2020 - People's Show, January 26, 2020
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
3. Fundamentals, 5th European Edition. Textbook. - M.: LLC "I.D. Williams", 2013. - 752 p.
4. Soliev A., Vuzrukhnov S. Marketing, market science. Textbook. - T.: Iktisod-Moliya, 2010. -- 424 p.
5. Ergashkhodzhaeva Sh.Yu., Kosimova M.S., Yusupov M.A. Marketing. Textbook. - T.: TDIU, 2011. -- 202 p.
6. Khamraeva S.N. Innovative development of rural infrastructure. Monograph - Tashkent: 2017 - 73 p.
7. Aaker D., et al. Marketing research. Ed. 7th. Per. s angl / Pod red. S. Bozhuk. - SPb.: Peter, 2004, - 848 p.
8. Aksunova G.N. Marketing. - T., 2005. -- 463 p.
9. Bagiev G.L., Tarasevich V.M., Ann X. Marketing: 3rd ed. / Under total. ed. G.L. Bagieva. - SPb.: Peter, 2006, - 736 p.
10. Basovsky L.E. Marketing: Course Lecture. - M.: INFRA-M, 2010. -- 219 p.
11. Boyuk S.G., Kovalik L.N. Marketing research, - St. Petersburg: Peter, 2004. - 461 p.
12. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. Problems in the Implementation of Quality Management Systems in Small Business Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 7. – C. 54-57.
13. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 71-75.
14. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 1-4.
15. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
16. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 13-19.
17. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 1-5.
18. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 06. – C. 113-116.
19. Azimovna M. S., Abdurozикович M. Z. Features of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE &

- INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 201-206.
20. Azimovna M. S., Shohruxhovich U. S. THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 110-112.
 21. Azimovna M. S. IMPROVING THE STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – C. 109-112.
 22. Azimovna M. S. et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 4-7.
 23. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 233-238.
 24. Azimovna M. S. The main directions of the marketing complex to increase the export potential of products //formation of psychology and pedagogy as interdisciplinary sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 20-23.
 25. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhruxhovich U. F. WAYS TO USE MARKETING INFORMATION IN THE PROCESS OF EVALUATING THE ENTERPRISE //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 9-12.
 26. Azimovna M. S., Shokhruxhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. ANALYSIS OF THE MARKET OF TOURIST PRODUCTS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 422-427.
 27. Azimovna M. S., Shokhruxhovich U. F., Rofejon o'g'li R. S. THE PROCEDURE FOR ORGANIZING MARKETING RESEARCH AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 392-399.
 28. Musayeva, S. (2022). DESCRIPTION OF MODERN MARKETING RESEARCH METHODS IN THE MARKET ECONOMY. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 33-38.
 29. Musayeva, S. (2022). IMPORTANCE OF MARKETING SERVICE IN ENTERPRISES IN THE CONDITIONS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IN UZBEKISTAN. Science and innovation, 1(A4), 280-286.
 30. Musayeva, S., & Raxmanova, A. (2022). Analysis of marketing activities in jsc" khovrenko" of samarkand region. Science and innovation, 1(A5),130-134.
 31. Musayeva, S. (2022). WAYS TO ORGANIZE AND DEVELOP MARKETING RESEARCH IN THE LABOR MARKET. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 99-105.
 32. Musayeva, S. (2022). PROBLEMS OF INNOVATION MARKETING DEVELOPMENT IN TEXTILE AND SEWING-KNITTING ENTERPRISES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 28-32.
 33. Musayeva, S. (2022). MARKET OF HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND FEATURES OF ITS RESEARCH. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 89-94.
 34. Musayeva, S., & Usmanov, F. (2022). WAYS TO DEVELOP MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN TOURIST ORGANIZATIONS. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 84-88.